

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES THROUGH INTERDISCIPLINARY CONNECTIONS IN FUTURE ECONOMICS

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Abstract. *Background:* This article presents the issues of developing professional competences of future economists through interdisciplinary communication, the analysis of the research work carried out by the scientists of the CIS and our Republic.

Method: In this article, focuses on primary fundamental training of prospective economists in their direction, a systematic approach to establishing interdisciplinary connections in the content of academic disciplines, improving existing objective connections between different fields, improving interdisciplinary engagement in teaching academic disciplines and courses.

Result: Thus, the formation of interdisciplinary integration allows the learner to go beyond the scope of one educational subject and apply the knowledge obtained from different fields of science.

Keywords: professional competence, interdisciplinary connection, higher education pedagogy, interdisciplinary approach, pedagogy.

Introduction. In the world, educational and scientific research institutions are conducting scientific research on developing the professional competence of economists, creating pedagogical mechanisms for optimizing the educational process, interdisciplinary communication, problem-based education, synthesis of knowledge, and improving the didactic information system. At the same time, special attention is paid to the primary fundamental training of future economists in their direction, a systematic approach to establishing interdisciplinary connections in the content of academic subjects, improvement of the existing objective connections between different fields, and improvement of interdisciplinary communication in the teaching of academic subjects and courses.

Modernization of the system of higher education in our republic, improvement of the quality of professional training of economists based on experience, further improvement of psychological-pedagogical and methodical training of students in higher educational institutions, formation of high-level competence in students have been created. In the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the direction of "further improvement of the continuous education system, training of highly qualified personnel, radical improvement of the quality of general secondary education" was defined as a priority [1]. As a result, opportunities for developing the professional training of future economists and applying the principles of interdisciplinarity in educational processes have increased.

Main part: In increasing the productivity of teaching the basics of science at all levels of education, only interdependence and compatibility are considered very important. It is known that the phenomenon of interdisciplinary connection is multidimensional. It is distinguished by the versatility of its content, the variety of teaching methods and forms. This forms the basis of the interconnection of the educational activities of future economists. The emergence of the problem of interdisciplinary connection in education arose due to the structural subject that helps to form a separate systematic knowledge of various phenomena of the real world in the minds of students.

Ya. A. Komensky, a classic of world pedagogy, said: "Everything that is interconnected should be taught in the same way, because this is very important in the formation of systematic knowledge [2]. He believed that in order to form a system of knowledge, it is necessary to establish a connection between academic subjects. According to Ya. A. Komensky, "everything should be taught." He believed that students should be given a comprehensive education that develops their mind, morals, emotions and will.

Another famous pedagogue and philosopher of the 17th century, John Locke, believes that each subject is considered to be its core (sturge), around which the knowledge acquired with the help of sensory organs is united. As such a core, he put forward the idea that the content of one academic subject should be supplemented with definitions, elements and facts from other subjects, not only to acquire knowledge about the basics of the subject, but also to acquire various skills necessary for their practical use.

Such ideas are also presented in the works of I. Herbert, a German pedagogue, psychologist and philosopher who lived and worked in the 17th century. He believes that the mental activity of higher education students is directly related to the connection between academic subjects. German pedagogue-democrat A. Disterweg, a follower of I. G. Pestolossi, also spoke about the need for interdisciplinary communication in the study of various educational subjects.

It is known that the idea of interdisciplinarity in the teaching of academic subjects of the higher education system is also widespread in Russia. Russian democrats who lived in the 19th and 20th centuries spoke about the need to acquire knowledge freely and actively. Scientists such as V. G. Belinsky, N. A. Dobrolyubov, N. G. Chernyshevsky, A. I. Gersen, D. I. Pisarev approached teaching with deep understanding against scholasticism and formalism. For example, V. G. Belinsky put forward the idea of "integrity" of the educational system, in which all academic subjects are taught together and interconnected. N. G. Chernyshevsky, in turn, expressed the opinion that the knowledge gained from one subject should bear fruit in mastering other subjects in the higher education program.

In the USA, the "Earth Studies" curriculum is included for senior courses, which includes "Physics", "Chemistry", "Geography", "Geology", "Crystallography", "Soil science", "Paleontology", "Biology" and other subjects. was also included. Students of the higher education system of England and France began to study natural science instead of "Chemistry", "Physics", "Biology", the contents of which were selected differently for different situations based on the science program. The science of natural science consisted of interdisciplinary knowledge of chemistry, physics, biology, geology, and astronomy. A serious drawback of this approach to teaching was that the subjects taught on the basis of integration were taught by one teacher, because the teacher did not have sufficient professional competence in imparting economic knowledge, so he could not teach at the required level for the entire course.

K. D. Ushinsky's theoretical legacy of pedagogues and didactics had a great influence on the development and development of the theory of interdisciplinarity. reflected. As a result, the following principles of the organization of teaching based on interdisciplinary communication were determined:

- determining the connection between academic subjects;
- elimination of various contradictions in the use of general terminology by economists of different disciplines;
- consistency in teaching the content of individual subjects;
- integration of knowledge from different disciplines;
- connection between theory and practice;

It is based on ideas such as working in interdisciplinary cooperation on the development of intellectual abilities of future economists.

Conclusion. Based on the above, it can be concluded that many great pedagogues who lived at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century recognized the need to implement interdisciplinary communication in the educational process, first of all, in the higher education system.

In the educational system, through interdisciplinarity, general concepts of the real world surrounding them are formed in learners. In psychological literature, the term "concept" is considered as a rational cognition, a mental phenomenon unique only to humans, an element of thinking and an elementary form of the existence of thought: a reflection of the serious properties and connections of an object or event expressed through words.

Thus, the formation of interdisciplinary integration allows the learner to go beyond the scope of one educational subject and apply the knowledge obtained from different fields of science.

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